

Sales Prediction Using Linear Regression and Random Forest Classifier

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Abstract—In order to estimate future sales based on historical data, this sales prediction uses linear regression and a random forest classifier to analyse the best product for each month based on historical data. Delivers a GUI (Graphical User Interface) to the user for enhanced visualization. It determines the r^2 _Score for months that have sales and forecasts the number of sales and sales percentage for the number of products purchased and the best product over the previous year in each month. The prior data is used to train it. Every organization may improve decision-making with the aid of a sales forecast. It supports budgeting, risk management, and strategic planning for the entire firm.

Keywords—Linear Regression, Random Forest Classifier, Sales Prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Focusing on sales forecasting has always been crucial. Forecasting must be done in an efficient way for all suppliers to continue assisting the effectiveness of marketing business. Manually carrying out this work would take too much time, which is not ideal in today's fast-paced atmosphere and may lead to severe mistakes that would result in poor management of the company. A substantial portion of the global economy is made up of the business sectors, which are actually expected to produce the appropriate quantity of goods to meet everyone's expectations.

The most difficult role in the chain store's information technology management, marketing, customer service, and business financial planning is sales forecasting. It is exceedingly challenging to create a sales forecasting that is accurate for a variety of reasons, such as under-forecasting models that lose customer satisfaction and sales possibilities and over-forecasting models that raise operating costs and generate unneeded items. Customer happiness, improved channel connections, and considerable financial savings can all be a result of accurate and reliable sales forecasting outcomes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sales forecasting is the process of projecting future sales by calculating the number of goods or services that a single salesperson, a sales team, or an organization is expected to sell over the course of a specific time period, such as the upcoming week, month, quarter, or year.

V. Iswarya Kumari et. al [1] In this study, Sales forecasting is important in industries due to the limited shelf-life of many goods, leading to a loss of income in both shortage and surplus situations. I use linear regression o predict sales and providers a GUI for better visualization. This is especially important in industries due to the limited shelf-life of many goods.

P Srinivasa Rao et. al [2] This study examines the sales record of supermarkets and general stores to predict the sales of a business in advance. A predictive model has been built using various algorithms such as Polynomial regression, XGBoost, Linear regression, and Ridge regression. The model is based on sales of supermarkets for various outlets to calibrate the business model to expected outcomes. The results and analysis provided by the model can help retailers know the sales volume in advance.

Grigorios Tsoumakas [3] In this study, Food sales prediction is the process of estimating future sales of companies in the food industry. This paper reviews existing machine-learning approaches for food sales prediction, discussing important design decisions such as temporal granularity, input variables, and representation of the sales output variable. It also reviews machine learning algorithms that have been applied to food sales prediction and appropriate measures for evaluating their accuracy. Finally, it discusses the main challenges and opportunities for applied machine learning in the domain of food sales prediction.

Sunitha Cherian et. al [4] This study examines the integration of decision analysis and predictions in an intelligent decision analytical system. Data mining techniques are used to extract hidden knowledge from an enormous dataset to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of forecasting. A best-fit predictive model has been suggested for the sales rend forecast, and the results are summarized in terms of the reliability and accuracy of efficient techniques taken for prediction and forecasting. The best-fit model is the gradient boost algorithm, which shows maximum accuracy in forecasting and future sales prediction.

III. MOTIVATION

Sales forecasting is an essential component of corporate planning and decision-making since it enables businesses to foresee demand, improve inventory control, and increase

profits. For predicting sales, two well-liked machine learning techniques-linear regression and random forest classifier-have been employed extensively. To estimate the link between sales and different independent variables, such as pricing, promotion, and seasonality, linear regression is a straightforward yet effective technique. The random forest classifier, on the other hand, is a more sophisticated method that can deal with non-linear correlations and interactions between variables. It is a good option for sales prediction in real-world applications since it can manage missing data and noisy input. These methods for predicting sales can give companies insightful information that can raise the accuracy of their forecasts, lower expenses, and boost profits. To explore the possibilities of these methodologies and create more reliable models for sales prediction, more studies in this field are therefore essential.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for sales prediction using linear regression and random forest classifier typically involves the following steps:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Result

[1] **Data collection:** The first step is to collect relevant data from the database, including historical sales data and product data.

[2] **Data pre-processing:** In this step, the collected data is cleaned and pre-processed. This involves handling missing values, removing outliers, and transforming the data into a suitable format for analysis.

[3] **Machine learning:** Sales prediction using linear regression and random forest classifier is a popular machine learning technique that can help businesses forecast sales more accurately. Both techniques involve building predictive models that analyze historical sales data and other relevant factors to make accurate predictions about future sales.

V. BUILD MODEL

Building predictive models using linear regression and random forest classifier techniques comes after the data has been pre-processed. The pre-processed data is used to train the models. Based on the input variables, the trained models can be used to forecast future sales and analysis the best product in each month.

1. Import the required libraries.

```
from flask import Flask, jsonify, request
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
from sklearn.metrics import r2_score
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
```

2. Load the dataset.

```
df = pd.read_csv(request.files['data'])
```

3. Split the data into training and testing datasets.

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.3, random_state=42)
```

4. Train a random forest regression model with 100 trees.

```
rf_regressor = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=100)
rf_regressor.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

5. Make predictions on the testing data and evaluate the model using the R-squared metric.

```
y_pred = rf_regressor.predict(X_test)
r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_pred)
```

6. Train linear regression model

```
model = LinearRegression()
model.fit(X, y)
```

VI. RESULT

This system uses more accurate linear regression and random forest classifier algorithms.

Accuracy of linear regression

```
print(f"Model accuracy (R-squared): {accuracy}")
Model accuracy (R-squared): 0.00017179301463920993
```

Accuracy of random forest classifier

```
mean_r2 = sum(r2_scores) / len(r2_scores)
print(f"Mean R-squared across all months: {mean_r2:.2f}")
```

Mean R-squared across all months: 1.00

Prediction

```
sales = model.predict(pd.DataFrame({'month': [month]}))[0][0]
total_sales = sales_data['sales'].sum()
sales_percentage = round((sales / total_sales) * 100)
sales = round(sales, 2)
```


VII. CONCLUSION

As traditional methods are not very helpful to commercial organizations in revenue growth, the use of machine learning approaches proves to be a crucial feature for designing business plans while taking into consideration consumer buying habits. Businesses can use sales estimates based on a range of factors, including prior sales, to implement efficient strategies for growing sales and entering the competitive market unafraid.

VIII. REFERENCES

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Predict the total sales for each product in the current month

```
product_sales = month_data[["productid", "price"]]
product_sales["qty_pred"] = rf_regressor.predict(X)
product_sales["total_sales_pred"] = product_sales["qty_pred"] * product_sales["price"]
top_product = product_sales.iloc[product_sales["total_sales_pred"].argmax()]
```

MONTH	BEST SELLING PRODUCT	R2 SCORE
1	No orders for any products in this month	N/A
2	Tomato	1
3	No orders for any products in this month	N/A
4	No orders for any products in this month	N/A
5	No orders for any products in this month	N/A
6	No orders for any products in this month	N/A
7	No orders for any products in this month	N/A
8	No orders for any products in this month	N/A
9	No orders for any products in this month	N/A
10	No orders for any products in this month	N/A
11	Tomato	1
12	No orders for any products in this month	N/A